

Research Article

Effects Of Inter – Row and Intra – Row Spacing of Three *Tephrosia* Species and their Influence on Soil Fertility.

Mbomi S E^{1*}, Anjah G.M.², Lamare D M³ and Oben F. T.²

¹Institute of Agricultural Research for Development (IRAD) Batoke, PMB 77 Limbe, Cameroon.

²University of Dschang, Dschang Cameroon.

³ IRAD Yaounde, B.P. 1457 Yaounde.

*Corresponding Author's E-mail: mbomisailieh@yahoo.co.uk, Phone number: (+237) 77 12 59 96

Abstract

A study was carried out to compare three space planting methods viz 0.5m x 0.25m, 1.00m x 0.5m and 1.00m x 0.25m on establishment, DM yield and management of three *Tephrosia* species. Seeds were tested and treated for percentage germination. The species studied were *Tephrosia candida* (Roxb) DC, *Tephrosia purpurea* (L) Pers and *Tephrosia vogelii* (Hemsley) A. Gray. It was a 3 x 3 factorial experiment in a split plot design with species in the main plot and space planting in the sub plot. The soil status of the soil was tested before and after the study to see the effect of *Tephrosia* on soil fertility.

Germination was lowest (58 %) for *T. candida* and highest (93 %) for *T. purpurea* with *T. vogelii* registering 90 % germination. The highest forage DM yield of *T. candida* (398.10 kg/ha) was obtained when it was planted at a spacing of 1m x 0.5m while those of *T. purpurea* (505.37 kg/ha) and *T. vogelii* (571.59 kg/ha) were obtained at a spacing of 0.5 m x 0.25 m. Only the DM yield of *T. candida* was significantly influenced by plant spacing. Averaged over species, DM yields after 12 weeks regrowth were 446 kg/ha at a spacing of 0.50 x 0.25 m, 427 kg/ha at 1.00 m x 0.50 m and 348 kg/ha at 1.00 x 0.25 m. The high percentage of germination indicates that direct seeding would therefore be an appropriate way of establishing these species for forage utilization. The wider spacing of 1.00 x 0.5 m can be adopted to reduce amount and therefore cost of seeds required for planting. Also when biomass is harvested, the material should not be discarded outside the plot but left inside to act as litter fall and affects soil fertility status.

Key words: Dry matter, management, planting density, regrowth, spacing, *Tephrosia* species.

Introduction

Multipurpose trees and shrubs (MPTS) represent an enormous potential source of protein for ruminant in the tropics and subtropics. These plants apart from serving as an important source of feed as browse material, provides enormous support in the maintenance and survival of the animal.

Gliricidia sepium and *Leucaena leucocephala* are two fast-growing nitrogen-fixing trees, which are particularly promising as browse (Carew, 1983) with considerable potential as multipurpose trees in the low altitude humid tropics (Sumberg, 1983). In the Western Highlands of Cameroon, their growth is hampered by high altitude (1300 m. a. s. l.) and the acid reaction (pH 5.3) of the soils. Hence, there is need to broaden the range of species of multipurpose trees and shrubs for alley farming, intensive feed gardens and other agroforestry technologies to include indigenous species which are well adapted to the environment. Browse species of *Tephrosia* offer an alternative. They are leguminous and nitrogen-fixing occurring naturally as trees and shrubs on hills, valleys, and roadsides of the Western Highlands of Cameroon, and are relished by ruminants. Shenkoru *et al.* (1991) have reported that *Tephrosia* species thrive in areas of up to 2880m above sea level with annual rainfall of 550 - 1900mm, and soils of pH 4.9 – 8.2. *Tephrosia* affects the nutrient status of the soil through litter fall and green manure and can also contribute substantial amount of nitrogen to the soil. However, quantitative information on biomass production and nutritive value of these indigenous browse species under traditional bush fallow conditions or under cultivation is scanty. Such information is needed for the development of appropriate management systems for fodder production as well as maintenance of soil fertility in the western highlands of Cameroon, especially in smallholder systems.

The objective of the study was;

- To investigate different space planting methods on establishment and dry matter yields of three *Tephrosia* species in the Western highlands of Cameroon.
- To study the effects of *Tephrosia* species on soil nutrient status.

Materials and methods

Location

The experiment was conducted at the Institute of Agricultural Research for Development (IRAD), Mankon Station, Bamenda in the Western Highlands of Cameroon (WHC). The station lies at an altitude of 1300 m above sea level. The annual average rainfall ranges from 1500 to 2000 mm with some places exceeding 3000 mm. The average mean minimum and maximum temperatures at the experimental site were 10.6°C and 25.1°C, respectively. The zone is characterized by a unimodal rainfall pattern lasting from mid-March to October followed by a relatively cool dry season period (November to December) and a warm dry season (January to March).

The WHC is characterized by ferralitic soils derived from basic rocks, the texture ranges from sandy clay to clay. They are classified as haplic ferralsols in association with rhodic ferralsols (Yerima and Ranst 2005). The soils are acidic (pH 5 – 6), low in organic carbon content and total N, deficient in exchangeable K and available P.

Soil sampling and laboratory analysis

Composite soil samples were collected at two depths, 0-15cm and 15-30cm before and at the end of field experiment. These samples were collected in March 2000 during land preparation and December 2005 at the end of the trial. Ten core samples were collected from random spots in the field, which was later (bulked to form the composite).

The soils samples were air-dried, ground to pass through a 4mm sieve and subjected to routine analysis. Particle size analysis was done using the hydrometer method. Soil pH was determined in a 1:2.5(w/v) soil water suspension using the glass-electrode pH meter. Organic carbon (C) was determined by chronic acid digestion and spectrophotometric analysis (Heanes, 1984). Total N was determined from the wet acid digest (Buondonno *et al.*, 1995). Exchangeable Ca, Mg, K, and Na were extracted using the Mehlich-3 procedure (Mehlich, 1984) and determined by absorption spectrophotometry. Available P was extracted by Bray-1 procedure using the molybdate blue procedure described by Murphy and Riley (1962). Extractable aluminum was estimated using 1M KCl and analysed colorimetrically using pyrotatehol violet Barnhisel and Bertsch, 1982.

Test species and seed treatment

Three *Tephrosia* species were investigated. The Species were *T. candida* (Roxb.) D.C, *T. purpurea* (L) Pers and *T. vogelii* (Hemsley) A. Gray. Seeds were scarified to break dormancy by pouring four times their volume of boiling water (100 °C) and left immersed for one minute (IRAD 1990). Treated seeds were placed in Petri dishes lined with two layers of whatman filter paper and watered to its moisture holding capacity. Twenty five seeds were used for each species and there were four replicate. Watering and germination counts began 48 hours after the commencement of the experiment Hanson (1985). Counting and watering of the seeds were conducted every day for a period of 14 days after which any seed that failed to germinate was regarded as dormant and unviable.

Establishment

The experiment was conducted to determine the best plant spacing for optimum forage yield of *Tephrosia* spp. The experiment was a 3 x 3 factorial in a split plot design replicated four times. *T. candida*, *T. purpurea* and *T. vogelii* were in the main plots and planting distances in the sub plot. The three spacings were 1m x 0.25m, 0.5m x 0.25m and 1m x 0.5m. Main plots were laid out in a randomized complete block design with four blocks. Treatments were randomly allocated to the main plots and subplots. Treated seeds were directly sown on the field. The plots and borders were kept weed-free by regular manual weeding during crop establishment over a six months period.

Data Collection

At the end of October 2004, plants were cut back to 75 cm above ground level on the 2nd of November 2004. This is to allow uniform growth before regular cutting starts. No data were taken and cut herbage was discarded. Regular 12 weekly harvests commenced thereafter for one year, from December 2004 to December 2005.

Harvesting was done manually using a machete. At each harvest, total fresh herbage yield per plot was recorded. Fresh samples for each plot were sorted into subsamples of edible forage i.e. leaves together with stems of less than 6mm diameter (Tarawali *et al* 1995). The samples were oven dried at 60°C to constant weight for the determination of dry matter (DM).

Statistical Analysis

Data generated was subjected to analysis of variance using the general linear model procedure of statistical analysis (SAS 1995). Statistical differences among treatment means were declared at 5 % level of significance. Means were separated using Duncan multiple range test.

RESULTS

The soils of the sites (Table1) were clayey (>70% clay) acidic (pH 5.2 –5.3), high in total Nitrogen (0.30%). The C/N ratio was intermediate. Available Phosphorus and exchangeable bases at 0-15 cm and 15-30 cm soil depths were extremely low. Total carbon was 5.26% at 0 - 15cm soil depth and 3.86% at 15 - 30cm depth. At the end of the experiment the soils were more acidic (pH 4.56 - 4.61) but of higher total Nitrogen content (0.37% and 0.28% at 0-15cm and 15-30cm depths, respectively). Available P increased to 1.08ppm at the 0-15 cm depth over thrice the initial value but decreased at 15 - 30cm depth. With respect to exchangeable bases, apart from Ca which recorded an increase at both depths, K and Mg recorded decreases after the experiment. Total C decreased to 2.97% and 2.56% for 0-15cm and 15-30cm depths, respectively. Soil analysis revealed that there were many changes in the soil nutrient concentration between the first soil sampling, just before the commencement of the experiment and the final sampling at the end of experiment 1. Soil at 15 – 30cm depth was more impoverished i.e highly deficient in the exchangeable bases (Ca, Mg, K). Generally, there was decreasing concentration of most soil nutrients with increasing soil depth after the experiment. There was no Aluminium at both depths at the start of the experiment but it was present at both soil depths at the end of the experiment. The values were 0.0 and 0.11 cmol/kg respectively at 0-15cm depth and 0.0 and 0.24 cmol/kg at 15-30cm depth.

Table 1: Soil physical and chemical properties of experimental site before and after conduct of the experiment

Properties	0 – 15cm soil depth		15 - 30cm soil depth	
	Before	After	before	after
Sand (%)	7.68		9.68	
Silt (%)	14.72		16.72	
Clay (%)	77.60		73.6	
Textural class	Clay		Clay	
pH (H ₂ O 1:1)	5.30	4.56	5.2	4.61
Nitrogen (%)	0.297	0.367	0.223	0.284
Phosphorus (ppm)	0.32	1.08	0.57	0.38
Calcium (cmol kg ⁻¹)	0.90	0.62	0.41	0.44
Magnesium (cmol kg ⁻¹)	0.34	0.15	0.17	0.1
Potassium (cmol kg ⁻¹)	0.13	0.08	0.07	0.07
Total Carbon (%)	5.26	2.97	3.83	2.56
Carbon: Nitrogen	17.60	8.07	17.1	9.11
Aluminium (cmol kg ⁻¹)	0.00	0.11	0.0	0.245

Table 2: Percentage germination of treated seeds

Species	% Germination
<i>Tephrosia candida</i>	58
<i>Tephrosia purpurea</i>	93
<i>Tephrosia vogelii</i>	90

One determinant of forage DM yield is plant spacing. DM yield could be high under drilling or space planting. However, the most appropriate planting distance for optimum DM yield to be achieved has not been established under experimental conditions. Table 1 shows the effects of plant spacing on DM yield of the three *Tephrosia* spp. under study. The highest forage DM yield of *T. candida* (398.10 kg/ha) was obtained when it was planted at a spacing of 1m x 0.5m while those of *T. purpurea* (505.37 kg/ha) and *T. vogelii* (571.59 kg/ha) were obtained at a spacing of 0.5m x 0.25m. It was only the DM yield of *T. candida* that was significantly influenced by plant spacing. Averaged over species, the highest forage DM yield was obtained at a spacing of 0.5m x 0.25m although it was not significantly different from that of 1m x 0.5 (Table 1). Plant spacing had no effect on DM yield obtained during the dry month of December (Fig. 1). In two, i. e. July and October harvests, out of the three harvests, DM yield was significantly higher in plots planted at 0.5 m x 0.25 m than at the other two spacings.

Table 3. Effect of plant spacing on DM yields of three *Tephrosia* species

Species	Plant Spacing		
	1m x 0.25m	0.5m x 0.25m	1m x 0.5m
	----- kg/ha -----		
<i>T. candida</i>	191 d	261 cb	398 bc
<i>T. purpurea</i>	367 bc	505 ab	409 b
<i>T. vogelii</i>	485 ab	572 a	467 ab
Mean	348 b	446 a	427 a

Values with the same letters in rows and columns are not significantly different ($p < 0.05$)
Means in a row or column with the same letters are not significantly different ($p < 0.05$)

Fig. 1 Effect of plant spacing on DM yield of *Tephrosia* spp. at different harvesting dates in 2005

Discussions

The experimental site soil was slightly acidic at the commencement of the experiment, but still within the pH range of 5.0–7.0 reported to be suitable for most plants to achieve maximum growth rates (Helyar *et al.*, 1990).

Removal of large quantities of *Tephrosia* spp. biomass from the field during the experiment would largely be responsible for the drop in pH, organic carbon, K and Mg observed at end of the experiment. Results of chemical analysis showed that *Tephrosia* biomass generated during the study period contained relatively high concentration of bases e.g. K^+ and Mg^+ , which could have had a liming effect if left on the field. This result corresponds with that of Lesturgez *et al.* (2006), who worked with *Stylosanthes guianensis*, a herbaceous legume and concluded that utilization of cultivated *Stylosanthes guianensis* in a cut-and-carry feeding system triggered accelerated acidification at a rate of $7.2 \text{ Kmol H}^+ \text{ ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$, as a result of the large quantities of biomass with high ash alkalinity being removed from the plot.

The increase in available phosphorus in the topsoil (0-15 cm) and decrease in the subsoil may be attributed to increased organic matter deposition on the soil surface from leaf fall, rapid mineralization of leaf litter and the ability of *Tephrosia* spp. to acquire P from sparingly soluble P pools in the subsoil. Because plants promote microbial populations by exuding organic carbon from their roots (Merckx *et al.*, 1985). Hence, the incorporation of phosphorus into microbial cells prevents its strong sorption to soil constituents, thereby maintaining it in a form that can be released subsequently into the soil solution following microbial turnover. The results also confirm that *Tephrosia* spp. is well adapted to low phosphorus availability owing to its rooting pattern and root characteristics (Rao, 1996), possible association with mycorrhiza (Sieverding, 1991) and ability to take up soil phosphorus from recalcitrant compounds (George, 2002).

Hot water scarification was sufficient to break dormancy in *Tephrosia* spp. seeds. Structural changes in the seed coat of *Tephrosia* spp. are needed, as is the case with a number of legumes to facilitate entry of water into the seed and these changes can occur within one minute of contact with boiling water (Ezenwa 1999). Germination was significantly improved and ranged from 58 to 93 % for scarified seeds in the present study compared to the 10 % (Shelton 1994) and 34 % (Babayemi *et al* 2003a) germination reported for unscarified *Tephrosia* spp. seeds. The 58 % germination reported for *T. candida*, in the present study is in close agreement with the findings (56%) of Babayemi *et al* (2003a). The high germination percentage recorded for *T. purpurea* and *T. vogelii* indicates ease of their establishment through direct seeding relative to *T. candida*. Direct seeding would therefore be an appropriate way of establishing these species for forage utilization or as planted fallows when introduced in agricultural practice under farmer's conditions.

One agronomic factor, which affects fodder yield, is planting density. Generally, the higher the planting density up to an optimum, the higher the fodder yield although individual plant yield decreases (Wong 1990). The absence of significant effects of spacing on DM yields in the present study was recorded for *T. purpurea* and *T. vogelii*, but not for *T. candida* indicating the absence of significant inter-tree competition which would have reduced total yield in *T. purpurea* and *T. vogelii* (Ezenwa 1999). Thus, the wider spacing of 1m x 0.5m can be adopted for *T. purpurea* and *T. vogelii*, the higher yielding species, to reduce quantity and therefore cost of seed required for planting.

Conclusion

For proper establishment, an adequate DM yield the three *Tephrosia* species should be planted at a spacing of 0.5 m x 0.25 m or at a wider spacing of 1 m x 0.5 m if seed are in short supply.

References

- Babayemi O J, Daniel I O, Bamikole M A, Ogungbesan A and Oduguwa B O 2003a. Preliminary studies on *Tephrosia* species: Effect of seed treatments on germination. *Nigeria Journal Animal Production*. 30(2): 209-216.
- Ezenwa I V 1999 Preliminary evaluation of the suitability of *Enterolobium cyclocarpum* for use in intensive feed gardens in South Western Nigeria. *Agroforestry Systems* 44:13-19.
- Hanson J 1985 Procedures for handling seeds in gene banks. Practical manual for gene banks. International Board for Plant Genetic Resources, Rome, pp 56 – 63.
- IRAD 1990 Institute of Agricultural Research for development. IRAD Annual report 1988 IRAD Yaounde Cameroon.
- SAS 1995 Procedures Guide for personal computers. Statistical Analysis System Institute Cary, NC, USA.
- Shelton H M 1994 Establishment of forage tree legumes *In: Gutteridge R C and Shelton H M* (eds) Forage tree legume in Tropical Agriculture CABI. Inter. pp. 132-137.

- Tarawali S A, Tarawali G, Larbi A and Harison J 1995 Methods for the evaluation of forage-legume grasses and fodder tree for use as livestock feed. ILRI Manual I. Teaching and Research at University Level 4-9 July 1982 Ibadan, Nigeria.
- Wong C C 1990 Availability and use of shrubs and tree fodder in Malaysia. *In*: Devendra C (ed) shrubs and tree fodder for farm animals. Proceedings of a Workshop in Denpasar, Indonesia, 24-29 July 1989 IDRC-276E Ottawa, Ontario. pp. 255-265.
- Yerima B P and Van Ranst K 2005 Major soil classification systems used in the tropics: Soils of Cameroon. Trafford Publishing, USA. 295 pp.